

1 **Chromatographic and spectroscopic characterization of urolithins for their**
2 **determination in biological samples after the intake of foods containing ellagitannins**
3 **and ellagic acid**

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14 **Abstract**

15 Ellagitannins and ellagic acid (EA) are metabolized by the gut microbiota to produce
16 urolithins that could be responsible for the health effects attributed to ellagitannin-containing
17 food products. Several urolithin aglycones could be present in fecal samples while
18 glucuronide and sulfate conjugates are mainly found in plasma and urine. So far, the lack of
19 available standards has made difficult their correct identification and quantification. In the
20 present study, UV and MS spectra characteristics of urolithins and their phase II metabolites
21 have been determined using different systems based on liquid chromatography (LC) coupled
22 with diode-array or mass spectrometer detectors with different analyzers (triple quadrupole
23 (QqQ) and quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF)). Chromatographic separation was achieved on
24 a reversed-phase Poroshell C18 column (3 x 100 mm, 2.7 μ m). Elution order, characteristic
25 UV spectra, and relative response factors (RRFs) with respect to their parental compound
26 (EA) and the most common metabolite urolithin A (Uro-A) were determined. This
27 contribution, along with the most important mass spectra characteristics (MRM transitions,
28 qualifier/quantifier ratio, accurate mass and fragmentation pattern) will allow the
29 determination of urolithin metabolites in different biological samples and their quantification
30 even if not all metabolites are commercially available. The methods developed in the three
31 systems have been fully validated in terms of linearity, sensitivity, precision, recovery, matrix
32 effect, selectivity and stability. After that, they were successfully applied to complex
33 biological matrices (urine, feces and plasma) from two human studies in which volunteers
34 consumed ellagitannin-containing foods such as walnuts and pomegranate extracts.

35

36 **Keywords:** Urolithins/ ellagitannin-containing foods/Relative response factors/ biological
37 samples/ UV spectra/ Mass spectrometry

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Urolithins constitute a family of metabolites produced from ellagic acid (EA) and
41 ellagitannins (ETs) by gut microbiota [1,2]. ETs are often found in different food products
42 including berries (strawberries, raspberries, blackberries), pomegranate, tropical fruits (camu-
43 camu), nuts (walnuts, chestnuts, almonds, oak acorns, pistachios, pecans), oak barrel aged
44 wines and spirits, and tea [3,4]. It seems that ETs release EA, which is then transformed into a
45 polyhydroxylated dibenzopyranone, the 3,4,8,9,10-pentahydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-
46 one (Uro-M5) and then undergoes sequential dehydroxylation to tetrahydroxy- (Uro-M6 and
47 Uro-D), trihydroxy- (Uro-M7 and Uro-C), dihydroxy- (Uro-A and IsoUro-A) and
48 monohydroxy- (Uro-B) dibenzopyranones [1,2,5]. Once produced these catabolic metabolites
49 can be absorbed, circulate in plasma and accumulate in urine as glucuronide and sulfate
50 conjugates or can be directly excreted in feces as aglycones [6,7]. Their absorption and
51 metabolism have been investigated both in animal models [6,8,9] and humans [10-12]
52 following the intake of different ellagitannin-rich foods. They have also been found in human
53 colonic tissues [13] and reach systemic organs such as the human prostate [14]. During the
54 past few years urolithins have received special attention because of their potential health
55 promoting effects [1]. Different *in vitro* and preclinical studies have reported their anti-
56 inflammatory and cancer chemopreventive activities [15-17]. The study of the nature of the
57 metabolites and their concentration in different biological compartments is necessary to
58 understand the health effects of ellagitannin-containing foods. Therefore, the development of
59 sensitive and accurate methods for the determination of urolithins has become a critical factor.

60 Several methodologies have been described in literature to identify and quantify urolithins
61 in biological samples, mainly based in the coupling of liquid chromatography to UV and MS
62 detection. Unfortunately, due to the limited availability of the majority of urolithin
63 metabolites these methodologies have not been fully validated and have mainly focused in the

64 most common metabolites (Uro-A and Uro-B). Considering the characteristic UV spectra of
65 these compounds [8], most authors use UV chromatograms for their identification, as
66 glucuronides in plasma and urine [11,18-21] and as aglycones in feces and bacterial cultures
67 [2,22,23]. Indirect quantification has been often applied in different studies in which it was
68 assumed that the UV response for the conjugates was the same as that of the commercially
69 available metabolites Uro-A and Uro-B [11,18,20,22,24,25]. Enzymatic hydrolysis of
70 glucuronide and sulfate conjugates has also been used for quantification, although in this case
71 relevant information about the naturally occurring metabolites is missing [12,19]. Some
72 authors have described the presence of other intermediate catabolic compounds (Uro-M5,
73 Uro-M6, Uro-M7, Uro-C, Uro-D) and their conjugates with the help of mass spectrometers
74 [6,8,26,27]. However, information in literature on the MS characteristics of these metabolites
75 is scarce, and only qualitative studies were carried out and relative quantitations assuming the
76 same MS response for the unavailable metabolites and the commercial standards led to
77 inaccurate results. The presence of several isomeric forms of Uro-A and Uro-A glucuronide
78 (Uro-A glur) has also been described [8,18,22]. Unfortunately the determination of the
79 substitution position was not possible solely based on UV and MS data without the
80 appropriate standards. In general, authentic standards are costly and their synthesis is time-
81 consuming. Therefore, most of urolithin metabolites are actually not well characterized and
82 this hampers their identification and correct quantitation.

83 The aim and novelty of the present study was to establish the most important LC, UV and
84 MS features of a wide variety of urolithins, using synthesized and purified standards, so they
85 could be used in future works where no commercial standards are available. For this purpose
86 three analytical solutions based on liquid chromatography coupled to different detectors:
87 DAD and two mass spectrometers (QqQ and QTOF) were used. The methods were fully

88 validated and successfully applied to determine urolithins in biological samples after the
89 intake of different ellagitannin-containing foods.

90

91 **2. Materials and methods**

92 **2.1. Chemical and reagents**

93 Standards of urolithins, urolithin A 3-glucuronide (Uro-A 3-glur) (**1**), urolithin A 8-
94 glucuronide (Uro-A 8-glur) (**2**), isourolithin A 9-glucuronide (IsoUro-A 9-glur) (**3**),
95 isourolithin A 3-glucuronide (IsoUro-A 3-glur) (**5**), urolithin B glucuronide (Uro-B glur) (**10**),
96 urolithin M6 (Uro-M6) (**6**), urolithin M7 (Uro-M7) (**9**), isourolithin A (IsoUro-A) (**11**),
97 urolithin A (Uro-A) (**13**), and urolithin B (Uro-B) (**14**) were chemically synthesized and
98 purified by Villapharma Research S.L. (Parque Tecnológico de Fuente Alamo, Murcia,
99 Spain). Urolithin D (Uro-D) (**4**) and urolithin C (Uro-C) (**8**) were purchased from Dalton
100 Pharma Services (Toronto, Canada). Urolithin A sulphate (Uro-A sulphate) (**7**) and urolithin
101 B sulphate (Uro-B sulphate) (**12**) were obtained as described elsewhere [28]. The structures
102 and purity of all compounds were determined by spectroscopic methods (NMR). **Figure 1**
103 shows the chemical structures of the compounds studied. Stock solutions of individual
104 standards were prepared by dissolving each compound in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to a
105 final concentration of 10 mM. Standard stock mixtures were prepared every six months at a
106 concentration of 200 µM dissolved in methanol and working solutions were prepared by
107 appropriate dilutions of the stock solutions with methanol. Internal standards, 6,7-
108 dihydroxycoumarin (DHC) and chrysin, were from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).
109 Stock solutions were prepared in methanol to a final concentration of 2000 ppm (11.2 mM).
110 All solutions were stored at -20°C.
111 Methanol “MeOH” and acetonitrile were purchased from J. T. Baker (Deventer, The
112 Netherlands). Formic acid and acetic acid were from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Milli-Q

113 system (Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA) ultrapure water was used throughout this experiment.
114 All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

115

116 **2.2. Samples**

117 Urine, feces and plasma samples were obtained from two pilot human studies after
118 consumption of different ellagitannin-containing foods. Studies were approved by the CSIC
119 Ethics Committee (Madrid, Spain) and all volunteers gave their written informed consent.
120 In the first study, 10 healthy volunteers aged between 21 and 55 years consumed 30 g of
121 peeled walnuts per day for 3 days (5.1 mg/g free EA after hydrolysis). After the last intake,
122 24h urine samples and feces were collected and stored at -20°C.
123 In the second study, 10 healthy volunteers aged between 18 and 23 years ingested four
124 capsules of pomegranate extract in a single intake (450 mg/g capsule; 122 mg/g free EA after
125 hydrolysis). Plasma samples were collected 24 h after the intake and were stored at -20°C.
126 Samples from volunteers consuming their usual diet but avoiding ellagitannin-containing food
127 products were used as blank sample for validation studies.

128

129 **2.3. Sample extraction**

130 *Urine samples* were thawed, vortexed for 30s, centrifuged at 14,000 g (Eppendorf 5804R,
131 Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany) for 10 min and filtered through a 0.22 µm PVDF filter
132 (Millipore). Samples were diluted 1:2 with water containing 0.1% formic acid before analysis
133 by HPLC-DAD or 1:5 before analysis by UPLC-QqQ and UPLC-QTOF.
134 *Feces samples* (1 g) were defrosted and homogenized with 10 mL of MeOH/H₂O (80:20) with
135 0.1% HCl using an Ultra-Turrax for 1 min at 24,000 rpm. The mixture was centrifuged at
136 4,000 g for 10 min at room temperature and the supernatant filtered through a 0.22 µm PVDF

137 filter. Samples were diluted 1:5 in methanol before analysis by UPLC-QqQ and UPLC-
138 QTOF.

139 *Plasma samples* (200 μ L) were thawed and extracted with 600 μ L acetonitrile:formic acid
140 (98:2, v/v) by vortexing for 2 min and ultrasonic bath for 10 min. The mixture was
141 centrifuged at 14,000 g for 10 min and the supernatant was reduced to dryness in the speed
142 vacuum concentrator (Savant SPD121P, ThermoScientific, Alcobendas, Spain). The dried
143 samples were re-suspended in 100 μ L of MeOH and filtered through a 0.22 μ m PVDF filter
144 before analysis.

145 Two internal standards (DHC and chrysin) were added to each sample. DHC was added
146 before sample preparation to control the extraction efficiency and chrysin was added
147 immediately prior to analysis to monitor variability into analytical instrument (injection,
148 ionization, detection, etc.). Final concentrations of both internal standards were 1 ppm when
149 samples were analyzed by HPLC-DAD and 0.1 ppm when QqQ or QTOF were used as
150 detectors.

151

152 **2.4. Analysis by liquid chromatography coupled to photodiode array and mass** 153 **spectrometry detectors.**

154 Three different analytical platforms have been used for the complete characterization of
155 urolithins. In general, they consisted of a reversed phase liquid chromatography system
156 coupled on line to a photodiode array and/or a mass spectrometer detector via an electrospray
157 ionization source (ESI). The same chromatographic method with slight modifications has
158 been developed for the three systems. For this purpose a Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column (3 \times
159 100 mm, 2.7 μ m) (Agilent Technologies) operating at 25 $^{\circ}$ C was used. Water:formic acid
160 (99.5:0.5, v/v) and -acetonitrile were used as mobile phases A and B, respectively, with a flow
161 rate of 0.5 mL/min. The linear gradient started with 5% of solvent B in A, reaching 18%

162 solvent B at 7 min, 28% at 17 min, 50% at 22 min, and 90% at 27 min which was maintained
163 up to 28 min. The initial conditions were re-established at 29 min and kept under isocratic
164 conditions up to 33 min. Injection volume was 5 μ L for each sample.

165

166 **System 1: HPLC-DAD-ESI-Q (MS)**

167 The instrument used was an Agilent 1200 HPLC equipped with a photodiode-array
168 detector and a single quadrupole (single Q) mass spectrometer detector in series (6120
169 Quadrupole, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Compounds were detected and
170 quantified in UV at 305 and 360 nm. Mass spectrometry with single Q analyzer was only used
171 to confirm the identification. Optimal ESI-MS parameters using nitrogen as nebulizer gas
172 were: capillary voltage 3500 V; drying gas flow 10 L/min; nebulizer pressure 45 psi, drying T
173 300 °C. MS spectra were acquired in negative ionization mode and measured in Selective Ion
174 Monitoring (SIM) mode. Fragmentor voltage for each compound was optimized by flow
175 injection analysis (FIA) of each standard at 50 μ M in methanol. A compromise voltage for all
176 the urolithins and metabolites to get maximum intensity of the peaks was 100 V.
177 Identification of all tested compounds was carried out by their spectral properties and
178 molecular masses.

179

180 **System 2: UPLC-ESI-QqQ (MS/MS)**

181 This system was used for the quantification of urolithins in samples containing very low
182 amounts of metabolites that required the use of more sensitive analytical techniques. The
183 instrument consisted in an Agilent 1290 Infinity UPLC system coupled to a 6460 Triple
184 Quadrupole (QqQ) mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).
185 Chromatographic conditions were the same as described for the HPLC-DAD system but using
186 as mobile phases water with 0.1% formic acid and acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid and as

187 injection volume 3 μ L. The coupling was done through an ESI interface with heated
188 electrospray ionization (Jet Stream Technology) that significantly enhanced the sensitivity in
189 ESI-MS by improving the desolvation and spatial focusing of ions. The following conditions
190 provided optimal results over flow rate 0.5 mL/min: gas temperature 300 °C, drying gas 11
191 L/min, nebulizer pressure 45 psi, sheath gas temperature 400 °C and sheath gas flow 12
192 L/min. All compounds were monitored in the multiple reaction monitoring mode (MRM) that
193 provides highly sensitive and selective quantification in biological matrices. Two transitions
194 with the highest intensity for each compound: a quantifier and at least one qualifier were
195 optimized, establishing fragmentor voltage and collision energy for each transition. The
196 optimization was developed by infusing 50 μ M of each compound into the mass spectrometer
197 with a mixture 50:50 of phases A and B at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min.

198

199 **System 3: UPLC-ESI-QTOF (MS/MS)**

200 This system was used for qualitative analysis, in order to obtain a more reliable identification
201 of the metabolites, and also for quantitative purposes, especially when metabolites were
202 present at low concentrations. The instrument consisted in an Agilent 1290 Infinity UPLC
203 system coupled to a 6550 Accurate-Mass Quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) (Agilent
204 Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany)
205 Chromatographic and electrospray conditions were the same as those used in the UPLC-QqQ
206 analysis . Spectra were acquired in scan MS mode with m/z range of 100-1100, in negative
207 polarity mode and with an acquisition rate of 1.5 spectra/s. Besides, MS/MS parameters were
208 optimized at a m/z range of 50-800 using a retention time window of 1 min, a collision energy
209 from 20 V to 40 V and an acquisition rate of 4 spectra/s. Data were processed using the Mass
210 Hunter Qualitative Analysis software (version B.06.00, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn,
211 Germany).

212 **2.5. Method validation**

213 Methods developed in the three systems were validated in terms of linearity, sensitivity,
214 precision, recovery, matrix effect, selectivity, carry-over, and stability of the analytes in the
215 methanol solution and in the biological matrices. Suitable internal standards were chosen for
216 adding to the samples during sample processing (DHC) and just before analysis (chrysin).

217 **Calibration curves** of a mixture of urolithins were prepared in methanol and in the three
218 matrices (urine, feces and plasma) from 0.0001 μM until 200 μM . Calibration curve in
219 matrices were prepared using blank biological samples spiked after the extraction with the
220 working solutions. The complete calibration curves with at least 15 concentration levels were
221 injected in the three systems to determine linearity **and limits of detection (LOD) and**
222 **quantification (LOQ)**. LOD and LOQ were calculated according to the IUPAC method
223 based on a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3 for the LOD and of 10 for the LOQ taking into
224 account the signals of the most diluted standard solutions.

225 **Precision** was evaluated by injecting a mixture of urolithins (10 μM in HPLC-DAD and 0.1
226 μM in UPLC-QqQ and UPLC-QTOF), prepared in methanol or spiked after the extraction in
227 the three biological matrices, three times in a single run (within-run precision) and in three
228 different runs (between run precision).

229 **Recovery** of urolithin standards in each biological sample was evaluated spiking in triplicate
230 blank biological samples at three concentration levels: 1, 10 and 20 μM and analyzing the
231 samples by HPLC-DAD. After vortexing, the samples were extracted as described in Section
232 2.3. Recovery was calculated by comparing the response of the standards in the extracted
233 spiked samples with that obtained in the samples spiked after the extraction.

234 Bioanalytical methods based on LC-MS should be also evaluated with respect to matrix
235 effect. The presence of this effect, due to the coelution of endogenous compounds during the
236 ionization, could result in ion suppression or ion enhancement. **Matrix effect (%ME)** for

237 each analyte was calculated comparing the slopes of calibration curves in solvent (methanol)
238 with those obtained spiking the blank samples after the extraction with known concentrations
239 of the analytes (post extraction spiked sample): $\%ME = ((\text{slope calibration curve in matrix-}$
240 $\text{slope calibration curve in MeOH}) / \text{slope calibration curve in MeOH}) * 100$. Previous works
241 assumed that if the ratio is within $\pm 15\%$ no matrix effect is present [29].

242 The **selectivity** of the methods was evaluated comparing blank biological matrix of urine,
243 plasma and feces with those obtained after spiking the blank matrices. The analytical method
244 should be able to differentiate the analytes of interest from endogenous compounds in the
245 matrix. Absence of interfering components is accepted when the response is less than 20% of
246 the lower limit of quantification for the analyte and 5% for the internal standard. Besides,
247 carry-over was assessed by injecting methanol sample after a high concentration sample or
248 calibration standard.

249 **Stability** of urolithins was evaluated in stock (10 mM) and working solutions (20 μM) during
250 storage at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 months and 1 year. Stability of urolithins under autosampler storage
251 conditions at room temperature were evaluated injected the mixture of standards every 12
252 hours up to 48 hours. A solution was considered stable if the peak area fell within $\pm 10\%$ of
253 the corresponding peak area in the freshly prepared solution.

254

255 **3. Results and discussion**

256 **3.1. HPLC separation of urolithins**

257 Liquid chromatography has been widely used for the separation of polyphenols and their
258 metabolites in biological samples, in particular of EA and their metabolites, urolithins. So far,
259 the separation of urolithins in complex samples has usually required long running times, often
260 more than 60 min, when conventional HPLC methods with columns packed with 5 μm
261 particles were used [6,7,10,18,21,26,27]. However, the wide availability of modern stationary

262 phase packing materials allows achieving good resolution and efficiency in shorter retention
263 times using standard HPLC systems. In this work we aimed to develop a single
264 chromatographic method, with slight modifications for the three systems used in the study, in
265 order to maintain the same elution order of the compounds. For this reason a Poroshell 120
266 EC-C18 column (3×100 mm, $2.7 \mu\text{m}$) (Agilent Technologies) consisting of a solid silica
267 core with a porous shell was chosen for the separation. The use of a column packed with
268 superficially porous microparticulates (core-shell particles) allowed us to develop a similar
269 LC method with both HPLC and UPLC systems. This configuration provided the advantages
270 of smaller totally porous particles ($1.8 \mu\text{m}$), but with lower backpressures [30]. Different
271 gradients were tested changing the gradient slope until no significant reduction in resolution
272 was observed. A compromise between analysis time and resolution was achieved, although
273 when a MS detector was used an improved resolution between peaks was not necessary.
274 The addition of formic acid in the mobile phase was essential to get better peak shape and
275 resolution [31]. Formic acid (0.5%) was used in HPLC-DAD system as a compromise between
276 better resolution and column lifetime and instrument deterioration. Even 1% formic acid was
277 checked although no much improvement of peak shape was obtained. However, when MS
278 was used as detector, strong ion suppression in ESI negative mode was obtained using high
279 concentration of formic acid [32]. There should be always a tradeoff between better
280 chromatography separation and ESI efficiency. Usually 0.1% formic acid concentration in
281 both phases (A and B) has been used in LC-MS methods because it is high enough to provide
282 a good peak shape without a MS detection reduction. Therefore, 0.1% formic acid in A and B
283 phases was applied when QTOF and QqQ were used as detectors.
284 Two internal standards were added in order to compensate for variability during sample
285 preparation and during the analysis. DHC was chosen for the addition before the extraction
286 protocol because of its similar structure and therefore similar behavior as the analytes of

287 interest. Chrysin was chosen for the addition before the injection because of its phenolic
288 structure and its elution at the end of the chromatogram without interfering with the analysis.
289 UV detection was recorded at 305 and 360 nm (see next section). **Fig. 2** shows HPLC-UV
290 chromatogram of urolithins under the optimal conditions. The parental compound EA was
291 also included to show its elution order respect to those of the different urolithins, as in some
292 cases this is the only metabolite readily available. Most of the compounds were well resolved
293 in less than 22 minutes. However, due to the large number of metabolites and the similarity in
294 their structures it was not possible the complete separation between Uro-B sulphate (12) and
295 Uro-A (13) and between the different isomers of Uro-A glur (1,2,3). Regarding Uro-B
296 sulphate and Uro-A, this does not seem to be a critical question because it is unlikely to find
297 both metabolites in the same biological samples (aglycones are usually detected in fecal
298 samples and glucuronides and sulphates in urine and plasma). The most interesting aspect is
299 the elution order of the compounds (**Table 1**) that could be very useful in future studies when
300 authentic standards are not available.

301 In relation to the isomers, recent studies have found several isomers of Uro-A and Uro-A glur
302 in different biological samples [2,18,22]. However, with the instrumentation used and the lack
303 of available standards it was not possible to distinguish between them. In this study, IsoUro-A
304 (**11**) and Uro-A (**13**), that only differ in the position of one hydroxyl group, were well
305 separated what is relevant to differentiate the two phenotypes described previously in
306 literature (phenotype A and phenotype B) [33]. For each isomer two different glucuronide
307 conjugates were analyzed: Uro-A 3-glur (**1**) and Uro-A 8-glur (**2**) and IsoUro-A 3-glur (**5**) and
308 IsoUro-A 9-glur (**3**) (see **Fig. 1**). As can be observed in the **Fig. 2** good separation of the two
309 isomers of IsoUro-A glur was achieved. However, isomers of Uro-A glur elute together as a
310 single peak, and despite testing different columns and methodologies that offer selectivity
311 alternative to C18 columns (Hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC),

312 pentafluorophenyl (PFP) and Diphenyl columns), the separation was not possible. As
313 described in next section typical UV spectra allowed distinguishing between Uro-A
314 derivatives and IsoUro-A derivatives.

315

316 **3.2. UV spectrum characteristics**

317 As we have previously reported urolithins show a very characteristic spectrum with
318 absorption bands at three different regions: band I (300-380nm), band II (240-280 nm) and
319 band III (280 and 300 nm) [8]. Here we have completed and confirmed this previous study
320 with the characteristic UV spectra of all the synthesized metabolites which are shown in **Fig.**
321 **3**. This UV information can be useful as a basis for identification of the different metabolites
322 in future work. Besides, isomers of several urolithins (Uro-A vs IsoUro-A, Uro-A glur vs
323 IsoUro-A glur, Uro-D vs Uro-M6, Uro-C vs Uro-M7) showed very different UV spectra that
324 allowed distinguishing them from each other.

325 Different wavelengths have been used previously for the detection and quantification of
326 urolithins (278, 305, 340 and 360 nm) without a valid analysis criterium [6, 7, 11, 23]. The
327 most characteristic and specific absorption band, common to all the metabolites, with the
328 exception of Uro-M7, was that with a maximum around 305 nm. Uro M-7 was better
329 determined at 360 nm, the characteristic wavelength for the parental compound EA, although
330 low absorption was observed for the rest of urolithins. Other wavelengths around 240 and 278
331 nm could also be used but they are not specific enough since most of the aromatic natural
332 products absorb at this wavelengths. All urolithins were then measured at 305 nm except for
333 urolithin M-7 that was better estimated at 360 nm.

334 Due to the lack of authentic standards, the commercially available Uro-A and the parental
335 compound EA, have been used as reference standards for quantifying the rest of urolithins
336 assuming that the UV response was similar for all the metabolites. In Figure 3, although all

337 the spectra are recorded at the same concentration, large differences are observed in the
338 absorbance of the different maxima, and this indicates that quantification of all the
339 metabolites as EA or Uro-A equivalents can lead to inaccurate quantitative results. Due to the
340 difficulty to get authentic standards, a single reference standard method has been developed
341 for the simultaneous determination of different urolithins by using relative response factors
342 (RRFs). Uro-A was selected as the potential reference standard due to its stability, availability
343 and higher content in most samples. The rest of urolithins could be estimated using their
344 response factors relative to Uro-A. To calculate the RRFs for each analyte the linearity
345 method was used [34]. The RRFs were calculated for each metabolite as the ratios of the
346 slopes of their calibration equation to that of Uro-A. The calibration curves and RRFs are
347 shown in **Table 1** along with information about retention time and maximum of absorption of
348 each compound. Although all the compounds have similar structures (with a coumarin core)
349 the RRFs varied from 0.13 for Uro M-7 to 1.20 for Uro-C. RRFs of the two available
350 glucuronides of Uro-A were close to 1 indicating similar UV response. The same behavior
351 was observed for IsoUro-A and its 3-glucuronide derivative whereas its 9-glucuronide
352 derivative showed less response (0.53). The sulphated conjugate showed also less response
353 (0.60) and indicated that the conjugation with sulphate decreases the compound resonance
354 and therefore the UV absorption. Uro-B and their conjugates absorbed less than Uro-A,
355 especially Uro-B sulphate (0.40) which was consistent with the results found for Uro-A
356 sulphate. Uro-M6 showed less absorption while Uro-C got better absorption than Uro-A at
357 this wavelength. RRFs have potential application to quantify compounds when their standards
358 are not available.

359 RRFs were also calculated related to the parental compound, EA, in case that this is the only
360 metabolite available. Results are shown in Table 1 with calibration curves calculated at 305

361 nm. Although 360 nm is the most characteristic wavelength for EA, response for the majority
362 of urolithins is lower or even absence at this wavelength compared with 305 nm.

363

364 **3.3 MS spectrum characteristics**

365 For a fast and unambiguous compound identification, the coupling of LC to MS is highly
366 effective. In this work the results obtained with HPLC-DAD were confirmed with single Q
367 mass spectrometer coupled in series and working in Select Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode.

368 For some applications, especially biological samples such as plasma and tissues, the
369 sensitivity of HPLC-UV methods is not enough for the quantification and the identification
370 only based in the mass provided by single Q is unclear. In these cases more sensitive and
371 reliable analytical methods as QqQ and QTOF are required.

372

373 **3.3.1 Optimization of transition in QqQ**

374 Detection on a triple quadrupole in Multiple Reaction Monitoring mode (MRM) results in
375 higher selectivity and sensitivity due to the double mass filtering. Despite these advantages
376 there are few works in literature that use this methodology for the quantification of urolithins
377 [12,27] probably because of the absence of available standards or at least information about
378 the most important instrumental conditions. In a recent work the same MS/MS conditions of
379 EA were used for the quantification of urolithin metabolites [27] what is an inaccurate
380 approach because of the different behavior of each compound during transmission and
381 fragmentation.

382 In order to get the richest relative abundance of precursor and product ions, the following
383 parameters were optimized for each urolithin: individual fragmentor (cone voltage) using Q1
384 scan mode and MRM transitions and collision energy using product ion scan mode. Usually,
385 at least two MRM transitions, one quantifier and one qualifier are monitored per compound

386 based on transitions from the molecular ion to the most and second-most predominant
387 fragment ions, respectively. The MRM transitions for each compound and the optimal
388 parameters are listed in **Table 2**. Besides, information about the qualifier/quantifier ion ratio
389 was used for confirmation of the identity of the compounds particularly after checking that the
390 ratio of signal between the two product ions was consistent between results obtained with
391 standards dissolved in methanol and in the three biological matrices (urine, feces and plasma)
392 with RSD below 8% (**Table 2**). This ratio has been used previously in literature to confirm
393 the presence of other metabolites [35]. So, although all isomers of Uro-A glur showed the
394 same MRM transitions (403>227 and 403>113), the differences in the ql/qt ratios between
395 Uro-A 3- and 8-glur (ql/qt=0.40) and IsoUro-A 3- and 9-glur (ql/qt=0.25) could help in their
396 identification in real samples. For other isomers (Uro-A and IsoUro-A, Uro-C and Uro-M7 or
397 Uro-M6 and Uro-D) the optimal transitions were even different for each compound and along
398 with the ql/qt ratio allowed their differentiation. To confirm their presence in real samples the
399 ql/qt ion ratio should be within $\pm 20\%$ of the determined value for each analyte.

400 Relative response factor in QqQ were calculated as the ratio of slope of compounds and slope
401 of Uro-A in methanol and in the different matrices. However, compared to UV, response
402 factors in MS are considerably less robust (RSD in most cases higher of 15%) because the MS
403 signal is subjected to the influence of several sample and instrumental parameters. For the
404 application of these RRFs in future works reproducibility studies in different laboratories,
405 with different instruments and over the time would be necessary. However, the information
406 about RRFs was useful to show the different response of the compounds in the mass
407 spectrometer and provided a plausible explanation for the wrong quantitation developed in
408 previous works when similar response of the compounds was assumed.

409 Although this QqQ approach is very specific, it leads to the loss of valuable information about
410 the composition of the sample as only specific ion transitions are monitored. Other platforms
411 as LC-QTOF could provide complementary information regarding the samples.

412

413 **3.3.2 Accurate mass and fragments in QTOF**

414 The compounds were also analyzed by tandem MS using hybrid system QTOF. This
415 technique is widely used for qualitative analysis because it provides a better identification of
416 the compounds based on their molecular formula that is obtained taking into account mass
417 accuracy (<5 ppm with external calibration) and isotopic pattern. Besides, information about
418 MS/MS fragmentation pattern adds certainty to the identification, especially for isomers that
419 show the same exact mas. The most important MS characteristics in QTOF are shown in
420 **Table 3**: molecular formula, accurate mass, collision energy optimized for each individual
421 compound and accurate mass fragments. Some of these features have been already described
422 in previous works [11,13]. Besides, due to the high sensitivity of this platform, QTOF is also
423 used for quantitation purpose when standards are available. RRFs were also calculated respect
424 to Uro-A in order to check the different response of the compounds in the mass spectrometer.
425 However, as in QqQ, the application of these RRFs in other works is difficult because of the
426 expected poor reproducibility over the time and in different laboratories.

427

428 **3.4 Method validation**

429 A complete method validation was performed for the analysis of urolithins in the three
430 systems described in this study. Results of linearity, LOD, and LOQ and precision are shown
431 in **Table 4**.

432 In general good **linearity** was achieved for all the compounds in the different instruments
433 with correlation coefficient $R^2 \geq 0.998$. Linear dynamic ranges ranged from LOQ to 200 μM

434 in HPLC-DAD, from LOQ to 1, 2 or 20 μM in UPLC-QqQ and from LOQ to 1, 2 or 5 μM in
435 UPLC-QTOF. Whereas LOQ values were influenced by the matrix, the upper limits of
436 quantification were the same with the standards in methanol and in the three biological
437 matrices (urine, feces and plasma). Linear calibration curve covered a concentration range
438 between 2 and 3 orders of magnitude, depending on the analyte and the matrix. Detector
439 saturation was observed at higher concentrations in the mass spectrometers whereas longer
440 dynamic range could be expected in UV. When sensitivity is not a limitation, extending the
441 upper limit of quantification (using HPLC-DAD) reduces the need for dilution and reanalysis.
442 High differences in **sensitivity** were observed in the three systems, mainly between UV and
443 MS as can be observed in Table 4. LOD and LOQ were calculated with the standards
444 dissolved in methanol and in the three biological matrices. LOQ values with UV detection
445 were in the range 33-148 nM in MeOH, 1,774 -6,024 nM in urine, 2,089 -7,326 nM in feces
446 and 447 -2,220 nM in plasma, depending on the analyte. The highest LODs and LOQs in
447 matrices (more than 50-fold higher than in methanol) were associated with high level of
448 background interferences present within blank samples (See **Fig. 4A**). LOQ values in plasma
449 were not low enough to allow an accurate quantification and more sensitive methods were
450 necessary. With UPLC-QqQ system, LOQ ranged from 3 to 115 nM in methanol, 4-124 nM
451 in urine, 6-116 nM in feces and 8-83 nM in plasma. The specificity and selectivity of QqQ
452 analyzer that operates in modes that provide very low background (see **Fig 4B**) originated
453 lower LOQ in biological samples when the limitation was due to interferences.
454 The QTOF system was found to be even more sensitive (up to 10-folds higher than QqQ for
455 some analytes) probably because of the new technology developed for this instrument
456 (iFunnel Technology). LOQs were in the range 0.5-6 nM in methanol, 0.7-32 nM in urine,
457 0.5-31 nM in feces and 0.9-32 nM in plasma. Using extracted ion chromatograms at accurate
458 mass, good selectivity was obtained with low background (see **Fig 4C**).

459 **Precision** was evaluated injecting replicates of a mixture of urolithins dissolved in methanol
460 and in the biological matrices. Results showed the range in which this parameter was
461 determined expressed as RSD (%). Within –run precision was in the range 0.1- 4.6% in LC-
462 UV system, 0.6-7.2 % in UPLC-QqQ and 0.2-5.2% in UPLC-QTOF. RSD for between-run
463 precision was in general a bit higher, especially with the mass spectrometers yielding values
464 0.4-8.7% in LC-UV, 2-13.5% in LC-QqQ and 1.7-12.5% in LC-QTOF.

465 **Recoveries** for each analyte and the internal standard (IS1) were assessed at three
466 concentrations in the three biological samples. Mean values are shown in **Table 5**. In general
467 good recoveries were obtained for most of the compounds and the extraction processes were
468 consistent and reproducible. Recovery percentages ranged from 84 to 105% in urine, from
469 44% to 95% in plasma and from 70% to 92% in fecal samples. The lowest recoveries in
470 plasma were obtained for Uro-D (61%) and Uro-M6 (44%), which could be related to their
471 similar structure (tetrahydroxy-urolithins).

472 Regarding the **matrix effects**, this is one of the main drawbacks of MS methods using ESI for
473 ionization. This was evaluated in both LC-MS system (QqQ and QTOF) by comparing
474 calibration curves prepared in the three matrices and in MeOH. The matrix effects of each
475 urolithin were expressed as deviation (%) of the slopes of calibration curves (**Table 5**).

476 Although dispersion in the results was observed, no significant matrix effects were observed
477 for nearly all compounds in the tested matrices (lower than $\pm 15\%$) [29]. Only some
478 metabolites showed low matrix effects with values between ± 15 and $\pm 25\%$. The 5-fold
479 dilution of urine and feces before the injection in UPLC-QqQ and UPLC-QTOF seemed to be
480 enough to maintain a low matrix effect. To reduce more this effect, higher dilution of the
481 samples could be made but compromising the sensitivity. Besides, in the present method, the
482 possible influence of matrix effect has been minimized by preparing matrix-matched
483 calibrator samples [36].

484 For the evaluation of the **specificity**, blank samples of each matrix were analyzed. As
485 expected, high specificity was observed with MS detectors (QqQ and QTOF) as no peaks
486 were detected in the elution zone of the analytes of interest. With UV detection, interferences
487 caused by endogenous compounds were observed (especially with urine and feces samples)
488 but their intensities were always below the allowable limits. No carry-over effects were
489 observed in the injections of methanol.

490 The results of the **stability** tests showed that urolithins are stable in stock and working
491 solutions during storage for at least one year at -20 °C (RSD was in all cases below 10%). No
492 degradation of compounds under autosampler storage at room temperature was observed with
493 less than 6% change in absolute peak area over 50 hours.

494

495 **3.5 Application of the methods for the analysis of biological samples**

496 The applicability of the developed methods was demonstrated analyzing real samples (feces,
497 urine and plasma) from two pilot human studies (n=10) after consumption of different
498 ellagitannin-containing foods: nuts and pomegranate extracts. Quantitation results from each
499 experiment are shown in **Table 6**. As previously reported [1], aglycones were mainly detected
500 in feces and conjugated derivatives in urine and plasma. Number of volunteers where each
501 metabolite was quantified was indicated in parentheses confirming the presence of the three
502 phenotypes previously described [33]: phenotype 0 (non- urolithin producers), phenotype A
503 (individuals that produce only Uro-A) and phenotype-B (in addition to Uro-A, they also
504 produce IsoUro-A and Uro-B). Chromatogram profiles of the analyzed samples in the
505 different instrument are shown in **Fig 5**.

506 Concentrations of aglycones in **feces** were high enough to be analyzed by HPLC-DAD (Fig.
507 5A). Intermediate metabolites (Uro-D, Uro-M6, Uro-C and Uro-M7), in addition to the most
508 common Uro-A, IsoUro-A and Uro-B, were identified and quantified. These metabolites were

509 previously identified in human fecal cultures [2] and detected in feces of different animals
510 [6,8,22] but only a human study reported the presence of some of these compounds in feces
511 after consumption of ellagitannin-containing foods [7].
512 **Urine** samples after the intake of nuts were analyzed by UPLC-QQQ and MRM transitions of
513 the main metabolites are shown in Fig. 5B. The high selectivity and sensitivity of QqQ
514 allowed quantifying even the aglycones (Uro-A, IsoUro-A and Uro-B) that are present at low
515 concentrations. Confirmation of the identity was carried out by examining the
516 qualifier/quantifier ion ratio described in section 3.3.1 and making sure it stayed within $\pm 20\%$
517 of the determined value for each analyte (values in Fig 5B). Due to the lack of standards most
518 of papers in literature quantified the conjugates after enzymatic hydrolysis [19] or using the
519 corresponding available aglycones [20, 22].
520 Concerning **plasma**, urolithins were present at low concentrations after consumption of
521 ellagitannins from pomegranate extracts, so the most sensitive UPLC-QTOF method was
522 chosen for the analysis. All compounds were quantified in the range of 10-200 nM, which is
523 in agreement with previous studies where a similar methodology was applied [13]. Extracted
524 ion chromatograms (EICs) of the metabolites detected are shown in **Fig. 5C**. Metabolites
525 were identified with high score (≥ 94) and low mass error (≤ 2 ppm). In addition, QTOF
526 provided useful information about other possible metabolites present in the sample.
527 Therefore, a new compound with molecular formula $C_{13}H_8O_7S$ was tentatively identified as
528 an isomer of Uro-A sulphate (IsoUro-A sulphate).

529

530 **4 Conclusion**

531 For the first time a wide group of synthesized and purified urolithins has been characterized
532 using three systems consisting of LC coupled to DAD and/or MS detectors (QqQ, QTOF).
533 The most important chromatographic (elution order), UV spectra (optimal UV wavelength

534 and RRFs) and mass spectrometry characteristics in the two analyzers (MRM transitions, ql/qt
535 ratios, accurate mass, accurate M/MS fragments) were determined for each metabolite. The
536 UV RRFs of the different urolithins compared with the UV spectrum of the most available
537 Uro-A and the parental compound EA are particularly relevant for urolithin quantification and
538 identification. These features could be very useful in future studies for the identification and
539 quantification of all metabolites when standards are not available. The methodologies have
540 been fully validated for their application in different biological samples (urine, feces and
541 plasma). Although HPLC-DAD is the most accessible technique and provide high linear
542 dynamic range and good repeatability, the application of high-resolution MS reduce
543 interferences and improve the sensitivity, allowing the quantification of compounds which
544 were previously not achievable. The applicability of the methods was demonstrated by
545 analyzing urine, feces and plasma samples after consumption of different sources of
546 ellagitannins.

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Caption Figures

Fig. 1 Chemical structures of the urolithin metabolites studied and the parental compound, ellagic acid (EA). (1) Uro-A 3-glur (2) Uro-A 8-glur (3) IsoUro-A 9-glur (4) Uro-D (5) IsoUro-A 3-glur (6) Uro-M6 (7) Uro-A sulphate (8) Uro-C (9) Uro-M7 (10) Uro-B glur (11) IsoUro-A (12) Uro-B sulphate (13) Uro-A (14) Uro-B.

Fig. 2 Representative HPLC-UV chromatograms at 305 nm of a mixture of urolithin standards under the optimal conditions. Peak numbers are the same as those shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Fig. 3. Typical UV spectra of ellagic acid and urolithin metabolites.

Fig. 4 (A) Chromatogram at 305 nm of 1 μM Uro-A 3-glur and IsoUro-A 3-glur in MeOH and in urine analyzed by HPLC-DAD. (B) MRM transition (403>227) of 0.05 μM Uro-A 3-glur and IsoUro-A 3-glur in MeOH and in urine analyzed by UPLC-QqQ (C) Extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of 0.01 μM Uro-A 3-glur and IsoUro-A 3-glur in MeOH and in urine analyzed by UPLC-QTOF.

Fig. 5 (A) HPLC-UV chromatogram at 305 nm of the fecal sample of one volunteer after consumption of nuts; (B) MRM transitions of urolithins quantified in the urine of one volunteer after consumption of nuts; (C) Extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of metabolites quantified in plasma of one volunteer after consumption of pomegranate. In parentheses score and error (ppm) for the identification of each metabolite was showed. Peaks: (1) Uro-A 3-glur (5) IsoUro A 3-glur (6) Uro-M6 (7) Uro-A sulphate (8) Uro-C (9) Uro-M7 (10) Uro-B glur (11) IsoUro-A (12) Uro-B sulphate (13) Uro-A (14) Uro-B.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

Table 1. Chromatographic and UV spectrum characteristics of a wide variety of urolithin standards: retention properties, relative response factors calculated respect to Uro-A and EA at 305 nm and maximum of absorption.

	No	Retention Time (min)	Regression equations (305nm)	RRF ^a	RRF ^b	λ_{max}
IS (DHC)	IS	7.16				256,296,344
Uro-A 3-glur	1	9.81	$y=27.84x+25.45$	0.85	1.57	238, 278, 302, 348
Uro-A 8 glur	2	9.80	$y=30.49x+1.62$	0.93	1.72	238, 278, 302, 348
Isouro A-9 glur	3	9.89	$y=17.44x-17.46$	0.53	0.99	254, 300, 330
Uro-D	4	9.94	$y=31.21x+24.63$	0.95	1.76	240, 262, 302, 240
Isouro A 3-glur	5	10.28	$y=25.88x+15.67$	0.79	1.46	256, 298, 326
EA	EA	10.73	$y=17.69x+3.077$	0.54	1.00	254,305,370
Uro-M6	6	11.49	$y=18.33x+14.11$	0.56	1.04	260, 300, 350
Uro A-sulphate	7	11.68	$y=19.89x+9.34$	0.60	1.12	238, 278, 302, 342
Uro-C	8	12.37	$y=39.54x+24.19$	1.20	2.23	258, 306, 340
Uro-M7	9	13.59	$y=4.15+6.05$	0.13	0.23	240, 286, 368
Uro-M7 (360nm)			$y=17.98x+4.83$	0.55	1.02	
Uro-B glur	10	14.37	$y=18.49x+10.31$	0.56	1.04	240, 274, 298, 326
IsoUro-A	11	15.73	$y=29.29x+20.15$	0.89	1.66	256, 300, 330
Uro B-sulphate	12	16.00	$y= 13.08x+4.66$	0.40	0.74	238, 272, 296, 320
Uro-A	13	16.16	$y=32.92x+25.07$	1.00	1.86	238, 280, 304, 356
Uro-B	14	22.11	$y=23.47x+18.84$	0.71	1.33	240, 276, 300, 332
IS2(Chrysin)	IS2	24.25				

RRF: Relative response factor

a) RRFs calculated respect to Uro-A at 305nm.

b) RRFs calculated respect to EA at 305 nm.

Results are the average of three replicates. RSD was in all cases below 3%.

Table 2. Optimized MRM transitions, qualifier/quantifier ratios and RRFs for a wide variety of urolithins and internal standards in QqQ.

	MRM transtions								RRF ^b	
	Precursor Ion (m/z)	Fragmentor (V)	Product ion (m/z) QT	Collision Energy (eV) QT	Product ion (m/z) QL	Collision Energy (eV) QL	QL/QT ^a		Mean	RSD
							Mean	RSD		
IS (DHC)	177	100	133	15	105	18	0.64	6.1		
Uro-A 3-glur	403	90	227	15	113	10	0.40	5.8	0.52	14.6
Uro-A 8-glur	403	90	227	15	113	10	0.41	7.8	0.46	17.7
IsoUro-A 9-glur	403	90	227	15	113	10	0.23	4.9	0.54	14.6
Uro-D	259	100	213	20	242	20	0.47	1.8	0.94	17.7
IsoUro-A 3-glur	403	90	227	15	113	10	0.25	5.9	0.68	16.6
Uro-M6	259	100	213	20	159	15	0.96	1.8	0.31	20.1
Uro A-sulphate	403	90	227	15	198	45	0.06	0.5	13.14	10.8
Uro-C	243	100	187	20	171	20	0.40	1.4	0.64	13.6
Uro-M7	243	100	198	18	147	20	0.38	1.5	1.06	14.4
Uro-B glur	387	90	211	20	113	10	0.36	3.5	0.75	17.3
IsoUro-A	227	100	171	25	159	20	0.75	1.7	1.77	12.4
Uro B-sulphate	291	90	211	15	167	35	0.04	4.5	32.08	14.5
Uro-A	227	100	198	25	182	25	0.34	4.3	1.00	
Uro-B	211	100	167	20	139	25	0.62	2.0	0.31	6.9
IS2 (Chrysin)	253	90	143	25	209	10	0.84	1.9		

QT: quantifier ion; QL: qualifier ion; QL/QT ratio of qualifier to quantifier transitions peak area for the confirmation of the identity.

a) Mean and RSD of QL/QT ratio calculated in methanol and in the three biological matrices: urine, feces and plasma.

b) Mean and RSD of the relative response factors (RRFs) calculated respect to Uro-A signal in methanol and in the three matrices.

Table 3. Characterization of urolithin standards by UPLC-ESI-QTOF

QTOF	Mass accuracy	Molecular Formula	MS/MS fragments	CE (eV)	RRF ^a	
					Mean	RSD
IS (DHC)	177.0193	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄	133.0294,105.0345	20		
Uro-A 3-glur	403.0671	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	227.0363, 113.0227	20	0.11	5.1
Uro-A 8-glur	403.0671	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	227.0335,113.0252	20	0.12	7.9
IsoUro-A 9-glur	403.0671	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	227.0348, 113.0222	20	0.08	13.4
Uro-D	259.0248	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₆	213.0193, 242.0222	30	0.95	15.3
IsoUro-A 3-glur	403.0671	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	227.0363, 113.0227	20	0.11	4.1
Uro-M6	259.0248	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₆	213.0195, 187.0404,159.0455	25	1.74	10.9
Uro A-sulphate	306.9918	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₇ S	227.0348	20	1.08	8.9
Uro-C	243.0299	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₅	199.0397, 187.0404, 171.0437	25	2.06	7.2
Uro-M7	243.0299	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₅	198.0324, 147.0451	30	1.29	8.8
Uro-B glur	387.0722	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₉	211.0408, 113.0233	20	0.13	4.6
IsoUro-A	227.0350	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₄	171.0452, 159.0455, 183.0447	25	2.10	8.1
Uro B-sulphate	290.9969	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₆ S	211.0405	20	2.03	5.3
Uro-A	227.0350	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₄	198.0321, 182.0375, 171.0452	25	1.00	
Uro-B	211.0401	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃	167.0500, 139.0542	25	0.60	12.8
IS 2 (Chrysin)	253.0506	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	209.0607, 143.0500	20		

a) Mean and RSD of the relative response factors (RRFs) calculated respect to Uro-A signal in methanol and in the three matrices.

Table 4. Results of the evaluation of linearity, limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) and precision (within-run and between-run) in the three systems (HPLC-DAD, UPLC-QQQ and UPL-QTOF) using standards dissolved in methanol and in the three biological samples (urine, feces and plasma).

		Calibration range (μM) ^a	LOD (nM)				LOQ (nM)				Within-run precision (RSD%) ^b	Between-run Precision (RSD%) ^b
			MeOH	Urine	Feces	Plasma	MeOH	Urine	Feces	Plasma		
Uro-A 3-glur	DAD	LOQ-200	10.4	710.9	903.5	164.8	34.8	2369.8	3011.6	549.3	1.0-3.3	0.4-5.7
	QQQ	LOQ-20	22.7	18.3	21.6	11.2	75.8	61.0	71.9	37.2	2.5-4.8	2.0-11.9
	QTOF	LOQ-5	1.5	7.3	6.7	9.6	5.0	24.4	22.2	32.1	0.6-3.8	5.0-11.8
Uro-A 8-glur	DAD	LOQ-200	10.0	523.3	626.9	173.1	33.4	1744.2	2089.6	577.0	0.2-4.2	1.0-5.6
	QQQ	LOQ-20	24.2	19.7	18.3	15.6	80.6	65.8	61.1	51.9	0.6-2.4	3.5-8.6
	QTOF	LOQ-5	1.6	9.5	6.9	9.6	5.3	31.6	23.0	32.1	2.8-4.2	4.8-12.5
IsoUro-A 9-glur	DAD	LOQ-200	17.2	1022.7	1357.1	640.0	57.4	3409.1	4523.8	2120.0	0.6-2.1	3.2-5.7
	QQQ	LOQ-20	20.0	16.7	34.9	23.1	66.7	55.6	116.3	76.9	1.5-3.0	2.8-7.5
	QTOF	LOQ-5	1.6	7.8	9.2	8.1	5.4	26.1	30.6	26.9	2.5-3.3	3.6-11.5
Uro-D	DAD	LOQ-200	11.6	675.7	1306.1	189.0	38.6	2252.3	4353.8	629.9	0.1-3.0	5.8-8.1
	QQQ	LOQ-2	9.1	5.7	8.5	6.2	30.2	19.1	28.3	20.8	2.6-4.2	4.3-9.6
	QTOF	LOQ-2	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.3	2.3	3.2	3.7	4.2	0.1-3.2	4.1-8.4
IsoUro-A 3-glur	DAD	LOQ-200	12.9	877.2	1078.0	179.9	42.9	2924.1	3593.2	599.6	1.0-3.6	0.4-5.5
	QQQ	LOQ-20	19.4	16.2	16.8	15.2	64.5	54.0	55.9	50.0	2.3-5.0	5.6-11.4
	QTOF	LOQ-5	1.3	6.7	7.0	7.6	4.2	22.2	23.4	25.4	1.4-3.7	3.1-11.2
Uro-M6	DAD	LOQ-200	24.2	1206.4	2126.1	444.1	80.8	4021.4	7086.9	1480.3	0.2-3.8	6.5-8.3
	QQQ	LOQ-2	34.5	31.3	29.4	24.8	114.9	104.2	98.0	82.6	2.6-6.4	4.2-12.3
	QTOF	LOQ-1	1.0	0.6	1.3	1.4	3.2	2.0	4.2	4.8	0.8-5.2	1.7-12.5
Uro A-sulphate	DAD	LOQ-200	44.4	1807.2	2197.8	666.0	148.0	6024.1	7326.1	2220.0	2.0-4.6	3.9-8.5
	QQQ	LOQ-2	2.7	3.7	5.4	4.3	9.1	12.2	16.1	13.2	1.7-6.7	4.5-12.6
	QTOF	LOQ-1	0.9	2.4	4.7	2.3	3.1	8.1	15.7	7.6	0.2-1.1	4.9-9.8
Uro-C	DAD	LOQ-200	10.2	668.6	1127.9	148.8	34.0	2228.8	3759.8	496.2	0.1-0.8	3.5-7.4

	QQQ	LOQ-2	10.3	10.8	12.2	9.7	34.5	36.0	40.3	30.2	4.1-7.2	3.4-10.6
	QTOF	LOQ-1	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.5	1.1	1.1	1.4	1.7	1.0-1.5	3.1-6.5
Uro-M7	DAD	LOQ-200	23.6	645.5	848.1	134.1	78.6	2151.5	2826.9	447.2	0.1-0.9	5.3-7.8
	QQQ	LOQ-2	5.0	2.7	5.0	5.6	16.7	9.0	17.0	18.5	1.6-3.7	7.8-11.2
	QTOF	LOQ-2	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.7	1.5	1.9	2.0	2.3	0.3-2.0	1.8-7.6
Uro-B glur	DAD	LOQ-200	21.5	1257.0	1828.6	336.4	71.7	4189.9	6095.4	1121.2	0.8-3.7	1.9-5.8
	QQQ	LOQ-20	11.9	13.4	15.5	12.9	39.7	44.6	51.5	43.1	1.3-3.8	3.1-11.0
	QTOF	LOQ-5	1.9	4.2	2.6	7.6	6.3	14.1	8.8	25.3	0.8-2.8	2.7-11.6
IsoUro-A	DAD	LOQ-200	16.1	995.6	1675.7	241.9	53.7	3318.6	5585.7	806.5	0.5-1.2	5.6-8.5
	QQQ	LOQ-1	1.8	5.8	2.1	3.6	5.9	19.4	7.0	11.9	1.2-4.1	2.8-12.1
	QTOF	LOQ-1	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.8	2.3	1.2	0.9	0.4-1.0	2.2-9.5
Uro B-sulphate	DAD	LOQ-200	39.8	1672.9	2011.8	596.6	132.6	5576.2	6706.1	1988.6	0.3-1.8	1.0-5.5
	QQQ	LOQ-2	0.9	1.2	1.8	2.2	3.2	3.9	6.2	7.5	1.3-4.0	8.8-13.5
	QTOF	LOQ-1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5	2.1	0.3-1.2	3.5-8.2
Uro-A	DAD	LOQ-200	14.2	1015.8	1219.3	252.6	47.5	3386.0	4064.3	842.1	0.5-4.3	6.0-8.7
	QQQ	LOQ-1	5.0	9.0	8.3	5.2	16.7	29.9	27.4	17.3	3.8-5.7	5.3-12.1
	QTOF	LOQ-1	0.6	1.7	0.9	1.8	1.9	5.6	3.1	6	0.2-1.6	1.2-10.0
Uro-B	DAD	LOQ-200	15.5	1127.8	2030.3	259.5	51.6	3759.4	6767.7	864.9	0.1-3.7	6.0-3.4
	QQQ	LOQ-2	17.2	37.5	19.7	18.8	57.5	124.4	65.8	62.5	1.1-6.0	3.3-9.6
	QTOF	LOQ-2	1.4	1.6	1.8	1.4	4.5	5.4	5.8	4.7	0.4-2.1	1.8-8.2

In UV all standards were measured at 305 nm, except uro M7 that was analyzed at 360 nm.

- Calibration ranges were the same with the standards dissolved in methanol and in the different matrixes.
- Range of relative standard deviations (RSD %) calculated with the standards in methanol and in the different matrices.

Table 5. Recovery of the urolithins in different matrices and matrix effect (ME%) evaluated in the two mass spectrometers

Analytes	Matrixes	Recovery (%)	Matrix effect (%)		Analytes	Matrixes	Recovery (%)	Matrix effect (%)	
			LC-QTOF	LC-QQQ				LC-QTOF	LC-QQQ
Uro-A 3-glur	<i>Urine</i>	95±3	-6.02	-14.18	Uro-C	<i>Urine</i>	93±4	-0.35	-1.58
	<i>Plasma</i>	74±5	-24.18	-2.46		<i>Plasma</i>	80±8	+5.30	+19.05
	<i>Feces</i>	74±5	+22.91	+3.34		<i>Feces</i>	82±7	+10.71	+9.38
Uro-A 8-glur	<i>Urine</i>	92±1	-18.74	+5.40	Uro-M7	<i>Urine</i>	85±3	-4.39	-14.65
	<i>Plasma</i>	75±6	-12.25	-11.20		<i>Plasma</i>	88±8	-7.07	-6.66
	<i>Feces</i>	77±4	-6.82	+11.63		<i>Feces</i>	85±4	+6.43	+0.44
IsoUro-A 9-glur	<i>Urine</i>	90±1	-19.85	-22.78	Uro-B glur	<i>Urine</i>	94±2	+1.96	-4.07
	<i>Plasma</i>	83±1	-10.30	-18.00		<i>Plasma</i>	89±8	-14.38	5.77
	<i>Feces</i>	76±4	+3.47	-6.62		<i>Feces</i>	91±1	+24.00	+13.99
Uro-D	<i>Urine</i>	105±6	-11.74	+10.31	IsoUro-A	<i>Urine</i>	83±1	-5.24	-20.02
	<i>Plasma</i>	61±4	-15.05	+21.59		<i>Plasma</i>	93±8	+13.32	-8.04
	<i>Feces</i>	76±6	+5.08	+11.42		<i>Feces</i>	87±8	+3.58	-6.01
IsoUro-A 3-glur	<i>Urine</i>	93±1	+2.47	-5.75	Uro B-sulphate	<i>Urine</i>	104 ±6	+3.01	-15.09
	<i>Plasma</i>	88±9	-18.1	+3.71		<i>Plasma</i>	95±13	-10.41	-5.42
	<i>Feces</i>	73±4	+20.21	+13.33		<i>Feces</i>	90±9	+20.06	+2.72
Uro-M6	<i>Urine</i>	103±7	-1.34	+11.02	Uro-A	<i>Urine</i>	88±2	-6.48	-20.36
	<i>Plasma</i>	44±4	-9.11	+10.09		<i>Plasma</i>	93±8	-15.02	-10.20
	<i>Feces</i>	70±1	+14.97	+19.08		<i>Feces</i>	87±6	-25.66	-21.54
Uro A-sulphate	<i>Urine</i>	105±3	-1.28	-13.03	Uro-B	<i>Urine</i>	84±1	-1.24	-19.60
	<i>Plasma</i>	90±13	-4.47	-3.48		<i>Plasma</i>	92±8	-9.60	+15.80
	<i>Feces</i>	92±8	+12.76	+5.79		<i>Feces</i>	89±3	+22.98	-5.22

Table 6. Concentration of urolithin metabolites in feces, urine and plasma of two human studies after the intake of different ellagitannin-containing food.

Metabolites	Walnut		Pomegranate
	Feces ^a Mean±SD (N) (µg/g)	Urine ^b Mean±SD (N) (mg/24 h)	Plasma ^c Mean±SD (N) (µM)
Uro-A 3-glur	-	70.0±57.4 (9)	0.171±0.151 (9)
Uro-A 8-glur	-	-	-
IsoUro-A 9-glur	-	-	-
Uro-D	6.4±1.4 (2)	-	-
IsoUro-A 3-glur	-	34.3±36.3 (2)	0.153±0.152 (2)
Uro-M6	17.2±7.3 (5)	-	-
Uro A-sulphate	-	-	0.034±0.040 (7)
Uro-C	74.4±88.0 (7)	-	-
Uro-M7	49.9 ±38.4 (5)	-	-
Uro-B glur	-	88.8±1.2 (2)	0.028±0.024 (2)
IsoUro-A	217.8±291.9 (2)	1.0±0.60 (3)	-
Uro B-sulphate	-	-	0.030 (1)
Uro-A	121.2±85.0 (8)	1.7±1.5(5)	n.q.
Uro-B	108.6±155.4 (3)	1.0±0.6 (2)	n.q.

N: number of volunteers where each metabolite was detected and quantified; n.q.: detected but not quantified (below LOQ); a) quantified with HPLC-DAD; b) quantified with UPLC-QQQ; c) quantified with UPLC-QTOF